

SAADI SHIRAZI ON THE MENTAL ABILITIES OF A PERSON AND THEIR ROLE IN HUMAN LIFE

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This thesis is about the mental abilities of a person and their role in human life. It was this idea that for the first time put human interests and life above all else, it was she who deduced the rule that only God can control a person's life and whoever violates this rule is guilty before God and people. When writing the article, the author used many scientific sources.

Keywords: personality, role, mental, upbringing, abilities, formation, development.

Since ancient times, the problem of man, the abilities of his mind, physical and mental capabilities have been the subject of research by scientists from different nations. At the present stage of human society development, especially in the context of globalization of economic, social and cultural life, these problems should be the subject of even deeper study. Scientists are still faced with the problems of exploring the mysteries of human nature, its capabilities and abilities, especially its mental abilities, as well as the problem of man as a whole as an object of research.

The ancient Greek scientist and thinker Socrates was one of the first to draw attention to the problem of studying human abilities and capabilities, his talent. Scientists are interested in his observations and conclusions about the essence of human nature. According to Socrates, an intelligent, literate and talented person is someone who will finish what he started. The philosopher linked the development of human society, the unity of mankind, the preservation of peace between nations and the well-being of people with the human mind.

The problem of the human mind, its cognitive and mental abilities in the development of human society, the development of economic, cultural and other spheres of human activity, have also been the subject of close attention by scientists of the East. For them, it was important to study the role of human mental abilities in his formation as a person, to identify ways to improve and develop human mental abilities. Saadi Shirazi belongs to such scientists who have shown close attention to the issues of intelligent activity and human mental abilities. In his works, the thinker attached great importance to the problems of

the human mind, its cognitive and mental abilities. The study of Saadi Shirazi's work shows that the thinker sought, as far as possible, to substantiate and show ways and methods of forming and developing human cognitive abilities, especially human mental abilities, in order to thus contribute to the upbringing of a full-fledged personality.

Saadi Shirazi was well aware of the need to develop the mental abilities of every person, and therefore in his works he called on people to master knowledge, develop their mental and intellectual abilities, and improve their cognitive and educational level. In his opinion, the correct organization of the work of "maktab" (maktab-school-author) should contribute to the acquisition of knowledge, increase the cognitive and mental abilities of each person.

It should be noted that Saadi Shirazi urged people to master scientific knowledge and improve their educational level, develop cognitive abilities in order to develop their mental abilities. According to the thinker, a person can rise to a higher standard of living only with the help of his mental abilities. Saadi Shirazi in his works paid special attention to the role of scientific knowledge in the development of human mental abilities and his formation as a person. He also associated the improvement of a person's moral qualities with a person's mental abilities.

Saadi Shirazi argued that the human mind plays a crucial role in its activities, all other organs cannot be compared with the mind. He was sure that man differs from an animal not only by the presence of language, but also by his mind and mental abilities, he raises man to the degree of a higher being. On this occasion, he said:

Гуфтор ба ақл аст, киро ақл надодан,
Мар гову хару астару дигар ҳаявонро [3.223].

[Thanks to the mind, only man is given speech,
Which is not given to cow, donkey and other animals].

For this reason, the problem of the human mind occupies a special place in his works. In the works "Khon-ul-ikhwon" and "Jome'-ul-hikmatayn", the philosopher drew attention to the practical side of intelligent human activity, i.e. the role of reason in his life.

The thinker was sure that the beauty of a person's inner world can be determined only by how he will be guided by his mind in his daily activities. The human mind contributes to the development of his mental capabilities, allows a person to establish himself in society, be respected and enjoy authority among

others. Therefore, the thinker called on any person in various life situations to be guided by his mind, not to allow himself to relax and not lose his composure: "Andareftani gunoi hash va pokiza kardani nafs bad he ast, ki xar kore, ki he sei akl zisht ast, Nakunā [7,19]. ["The only way to identify your mistakes and purify your soul is not to commit unreasonable acts."]

Summing up his observations, Saadi Shirazi came to the conclusion that in many life situations a person is often guided by his emotions, neglecting his mind in his personal, often selfish interests, and commits not good deeds and deeds. Then we see that a person commits evil, his actions harm other people. The thinker was firmly convinced that a healthy mind and pure thoughts would push a person to good and noble deeds, and an unhealthy mind becomes the cause of evil deeds, deeds and actions. In his works, Saadi Shirazi, paying attention to the role of the human mind in the development of his mental abilities, comes to the conclusion that human knowledge is a product of his mind. In his opinion, the human mind is the supreme creation of God, and knowledge contributes to the development of human mental abilities, and only through science and knowledge.

Used Literature:

1. Abdurakhimov K.S., Sidikova Z.K. Talimoti ahlokii Saidii Sherozi. The moral teaching of Saadi Shirazi. – Dushanbe. 2007. 104 p.
2. Ashurov G. The philosophical views of Saadi Shirazi. – Dushanbe, 1965 – 113 p.
3. Kulmatov N. Akidaoi akhlokii sad. Saadi's moral ideas. – Dushanbe. 1981. – 170 p.
4. Murodova T. On some aspects of the theory of emanation of Avicenna and Saadi Shirazi. //Izv. AN Taj. SSR. Department of societies. Sciences. – 1982. - No.1. – pp. 61-64.
5. Saadi Sherozi. Guliston. – Dushanbe, 1962. – 440 p.

